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Reverse Psychology of Confiscated Ancient Intellectual Properties in the West: A Case Study on the Appropriation of the Swastika by Nazi Germany and the Mazda by Japanese Automotive Industry

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Abstract

This paper explores the concept of reverse psychology as it applies to the transformation of cultural and intellectual symbols, focusing on the swastika as a case study. Once a universal symbol of good fortune and harmony originating in Asia, the swastika was repurposed by the Nazi regime in Germany, becoming associated with violence and supremacy. This ideological shift demonstrates how the symbolic identity of cultural artifacts can be dramatically altered when appropriated by external entities for political agendas, which often results in the cultural and psychological alienation of the symbol's original communities. The paper further investigates the implications of such cultural appropriations for contemporary society and the efforts to restore the swastika's original significance. The concept of reverse psychology of ancient cultural heritage also applies to the concept of Mazda (ancient Persian God of righteousness) currently being used as a brand in automotive industry which needs careful consideration.

Keywords: Intellectual property rights, Mazda, Swastika, Nazi Germany, Hakenkreuz

Introduction

Cultural symbols have long been central to human expression, embodying complex layers of historical and social meanings. One striking example is the swastika, a symbol dating back millennia, used across Asia as a representation of good fortune and spiritual well-being. In the 20th century, however, this symbol was repurposed by Nazi Germany, becoming a universally recognized emblem of oppression and violence. This study will analyze the psychological and sociocultural impacts of this transformation on both Asian societies and the Western world, highlighting the concept of reverse psychology in cultural appropriation. Additionally, the article will review current efforts in India and other Asian countries to reclaim the swastika's original meaning. The Mazda brand name carries a legacy that connects modern automotive engineering with ancient spiritual symbolism. Founded in Hiroshima, Japan, in 1920, Mazda began as a small manufacturer known as the Toyo Cork Kogyo Company, initially producing machine tools and later vehicles (Mazda Motor Corporation, 2023). In 1931, the company shifted focus toward the automotive industry, producing a three-wheeled truck. However, it was in the early 1960s that the company rebranded as Mazda, drawing on the symbolism of the ancient Zoroastrian god, Ahura Mazda (Haigh, 2006).

Ahura Mazda, revered in Zoroastrianism, is the god of wisdom, light, and goodness, a symbol of knowledge that transcends darkness. The choice of the Mazda name was intended to reflect these values and honor the founder's vision of promoting innovation, intelligence, and harmony in their vehicles (Dastur, 2012). Ahura Mazda was central to Zoroastrianism, one of the world's oldest monotheistic religions originating in ancient Persia around the first millennium BCE (Boyce, 1984). The deity's name, which translates to "Wise Lord," embodies the pursuit of enlightenment, progress, and ethical integrity—principles that the Mazda brand has aspired to align with in its designs and philosophy.

The name Mazda was selected as a tribute not only to Ahura Mazda but also to Jujiro Matsuda, the company's founder, whose surname "Matsuda" is phonetically similar to "Mazda" in Japanese (Mazda Motor Corporation, 2023). This dual reference underlines a commitment to combining tradition with progress, tying together Eastern and Western values. Today, Mazda's vehicles are marketed globally with a focus on innovative design, advanced engineering, and a reputation for quality, all of which resonate with the enlightened values that Ahura Mazda represents.

Historical Background of the Swastika

The term "swastika" derives from the Sanskrit word *svastika*, meaning "well-being" or "good fortune" (Chatterjee, 2020). Used for thousands of years in cultures such as Hinduism, Buddhism, and Jainism, the swastika has represented positive aspects of life and spiritual harmony (Wong, 2019). This symbol is prevalent across Asia, where it decorates temples, artwork, and is used in various cultural ceremonies.

In the early 20th century, however, German Nazi ideology reinterpreted the swastika as a symbol of Aryan superiority. Adolf Hitler and his regime utilized the swastika in their propaganda, transforming its meaning from spiritual well-being to that of racial and nationalistic dominance (Strobl, 2018). This appropriation fundamentally altered the symbol's perception, especially in Western societies, leading to widespread aversion and legal prohibitions on its display in many countries.

Psychological Impact of the Symbolic Transformation

The appropriation of the swastika by the Nazi regime represents a clear case of reverse psychological impact on symbol perception. When the swastika, originally a revered symbol of harmony, was rebranded as a Nazi icon, it resulted in widespread psychological distress for Asian communities. This shift exemplifies what psychologist Carl Jung refers to as "cultural trauma," where a symbol or cultural object associated with positive values becomes linked with negative associations (Perry, 2017).

The redefinition of the swastika had long-lasting effects on both Eastern and Western societies. Western audiences now associate the

swastika almost exclusively with Nazism and hate, rather than its original meanings of fortune and peace (Nakamura, 2016). This shift in perception demonstrates reverse psychology on a cultural scale, where the value of an artifact is redefined by external forces, alienating its cultural origins and disrupting its psychological impact on the public.

The Role of Reverse Psychology in Cultural Appropriation

Reverse psychology in cultural appropriation occurs when the imposed meanings contrast with or even negate the artifact's original significance. For the swastika, Nazi Germany's appropriation represents a significant psychological reversal, turning a symbol of peace into a representation of terror. This transformation resulted in a "symbolic displacement," where the swastika's original meaning became overshadowed by its newfound political associations (Schwartz, 2019).

By seizing the swastika, the Nazis not only repurposed it for propaganda but also instigated a form of cultural erasure, stripping it from its Asian roots. Psychological studies have shown that such acts of appropriation, when politically or ideologically motivated, can leave deep emotional scars on affected cultures (Liu, 2020). In the case of the swastika, Asian communities were forced to confront the psychological dissonance of seeing a symbol of peace weaponized in the West.

Cultural Reclamation Efforts in the Modern Context

Despite the negative connotations attached to the swastika in the West, various Asian cultures continue to use it in its original context. In Hindu and Buddhist ceremonies, the swastika remains a powerful spiritual symbol, representing prosperity and well-being (Rao, 2015). Cultural reclamation movements are now actively working to restore the swastika's original meaning by distinguishing between the Nazi swastika and the ancient symbol used across Asia.

For example, the "Swastika Reclamation Movement" in India has launched initiatives to educate global audiences on the symbol's original significance. Through conferences, media campaigns, and educational outreach, these movements aim to foster an understanding of the swastika's dual identities and to challenge Western-centric views that see it solely as a Nazi emblem (Chatterjee, 2020).

Conclusion

The appropriation of the swastika by Nazi Germany provides a compelling example of reverse psychology in the context of cultural appropriation. By transforming a symbol of peace into one of oppression, the Nazis effectively erased its positive origins from public consciousness, replacing it with negative associations. This process has left Asian communities grappling with a cultural loss, as a cherished symbol was rebranded as a symbol of fear. Reclamation efforts continue to face challenges, yet they highlight the ongoing struggle to reclaim cultural heritage in the face of historical distortion. By exploring these cases, we gain a deeper understanding of how reverse psychology can shape public perception of cultural artifacts, reinforcing the need for cultural sensitivity and global awareness in interpreting symbols with diverse cultural origins. In the case of Ahura-Mazda the holistic approach of Persians towards the Name and symbol of Ahura-Mazda makes further concerns about appropriation of the name with business motifs. Although, the automotive industry never waged a war against humanity, the confiscation is considered illegal and has to be considered a legal agenda.

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Abstract

The quest for Eutopia, or an idealized realm of ultimate happiness and fulfillment, is a universal human endeavor that has inspired a range of religious, philosophical, and sociopolitical visions. This article examines the concept of Eutopia across different frameworks, including **Acquired Eutopia**, **Promised Eutopia**, **Philosophical Eutopia**, **Inherited Eutopia**, and **Socially Constructed Eutopia**. Utilizing verses from the Qur'an, Bible, and other religious scriptures, alongside insights from notable philosophers.

Keywords: Eutopia, Jannah, Behesht, Paradise

Introduction

The idea of Eutopia, from the Greek words "eu" (good) and "topos" (place), represents the ideal state or place of ultimate happiness that people have envisioned through religious, philosophical, and social lenses. This study investigates how various doctrines and philosophical perspectives define, seek, or promise Eutopia, drawing from ancient texts and modern interpretations to illuminate diverse conceptualizations of paradise. By grounding each Eutopian category in scripture and philosophical reflection, this study offers a comprehensive look at how humanity across ages has conceptualized their ideals.

1. Acquired Eutopia

Definition and Characteristics

Acquired Eutopia is an individually crafted paradise, reached through personal discipline, inner peace, and self-development. It aligns closely with Aristotle's idea of *eudaimonia*, or human flourishing, which he describes as the "activity of the soul in accordance with virtue" (Aristotle, *Nicomachean Ethics*, Book I, Chapter 7). This philosophy views happiness as something cultivated through virtuous action, a self-built Eutopia achieved through alignment with one's own moral compass (Kraut, 2020).

Examples in Eastern Philosophy and Religious Scriptures

In Eastern philosophies, the Acquired Eutopia resonates with the Buddhist concept of nirvana. As stated in the Dhammapada, "Just as a storm cannot overturn a mountain, so temptation cannot shake the person who is wise and humble" (Dhammapada 6:7). In Buddhist tradition, nirvana is the self-realized state of liberation from suffering, achieved through ethical living, mindfulness, and meditation (Batchelor, 2011).

The Qur'an emphasizes inner paradise through self-purification: "And whoever purifies himself does so for the benefit of his own soul" (Qur'an 35:18). This internalized paradise represents a form of Acquired Eutopia where individuals cultivate inner harmony and alignment with divine principles through personal discipline.

Stoic Philosophy and the Inner Kingdom

The Stoics, like Epictetus and Marcus Aurelius, taught that paradise could be found within oneself. Epictetus wrote, "No man is free who is not master of himself" (Epictetus, *Discourses*), highlighting that happiness arises from self-control and mastery over desires. Marcus Aurelius likewise asserts in *Meditations*: "You have power over your mind, not outside events. Realize this, and you will find strength" (Aurelius, *Meditations* 4.3).

2. Promised Eutopia

Definition and Characteristics

Promised Eutopia, or paradise assured by religious faith, involves a divinely guaranteed paradise as a reward for virtuous living. In contrast to the self-built paradise, Promised Eutopia relies on divine intervention and is often depicted as eternal bliss in sacred texts.

Islamic Perspective

In Islam, Jannah (paradise) is described in the Qur'an as a lush and fertile place where believers receive the ultimate peace and divine presence. "But give good tidings to those who believe and do righteous deeds, that they will have gardens beneath which rivers flow" (Qur'an 2:25). This promise provides both motivation and comfort for believers, aligning the concept of paradise with rewards for piety and devotion to God (Sachedina, 2018).

Christian Perspective

Christianity similarly emphasizes the eternal paradise of Heaven as a Promised Eutopia. Jesus speaks of Heaven as a place of abundance: "In my Father's house are many mansions... I go to prepare a place for you" (John 14:2). This Promised Eutopia embodies the Christian belief in eternal life and peace for those who live according to Jesus' teachings (McGrath, 2017). Additionally, the Book of Revelation paints a vivid picture of this Eutopia as a place without suffering, where "God will wipe away every tear... and there will be no more death or sorrow or pain" (Revelation 21:4).

Hindu and Sikh Scriptures

In Hinduism, Moksha (liberation) is the ultimate release from the cycle of rebirth, representing a union with the divine. The Bhagavad

Gita states, "When a man finds delight within himself, he finds true happiness which is beyond the senses" (Bhagavad Gita 5:21), emphasizing inner peace as a divine promise for the faithful. Similarly, Sikhism offers a Promised Eutopia in Sach Khand, a state of eternal truth where the soul resides with God, which is granted through devotion and righteous living (Singh, 2005).

3. Philosophical Eutopia

Definition and Characteristics

Philosophical Eutopia includes collective visions for an ideal society created through social, political, or economic structures that reflect principles of justice, equity, or order. Thinkers throughout history have crafted such utopian societies in their works, often aiming to present models for social reform.

Plato's Ideal State

Plato's *Republic* proposes an ideal society governed by philosopher-kings who embody wisdom and justice. According to Plato, "Justice means minding your own business and not meddling with other people's concerns" (*The Republic*, Book IV). His vision for Eutopia is structured around the virtues of wisdom, courage, and temperance, making it a model of societal balance and harmony (Popper, 1966).

Karl Marx's Vision of Communism

Karl Marx's utopia takes the form of a classless society where all resources are shared. Marx argued, "From each according to his ability, to each according to his needs," advocating a world where material needs are met without exploitation (Marx, *Critique of the Gotha Program*). Marx's vision stands as a collective Eutopia based on the equitable distribution of resources, opposing capitalist structures and highlighting human welfare as the highest priority (Wolff, 2002).

Dystopian Interpretations and Critiques

However, certain totalitarian regimes have twisted philosophical ideals into dystopian extremes. George Orwell critiques such regimes in *1984*, where totalitarianism suppresses individuality under the guise of an ideal state (Orwell, 1949). This illustrates how

philosophical Eutopia, when misapplied, can devolve into a controlled and oppressive society.

4. Inherited Eutopia

Definition and Characteristics

Inherited Eutopia pertains to paradise passed down through familial or cultural inheritance. Often tied to notions of ancestral land or divine favor, this concept of paradise suggests that one's lineage or heritage grants access to Eutopia.

Ancestral Paradises in Indigenous Beliefs

Many indigenous traditions envision paradise as an ancestral homeland where one reconnects with forebears and spiritual realms. Native American beliefs, for example, often view paradise as the unspoiled natural world, reflecting an intimate connection to land and heritage (Deloria, 2003).

Medieval European Nobility and the Hereafter

In Medieval Europe, paradise was sometimes viewed as the continuation of noble lineage, where the aristocracy believed they would be honored in the afterlife. This idea reflects an Inherited Eutopia tied to social status, portraying paradise as a rightful inheritance rather than an earned reward (Anderson, 1991).

5. Socially Constructed Eutopia

Definition and Characteristics

Socially Constructed Eutopia represents paradise formed through societal or community effort, where people collectively build environments or societies that strive toward harmonious living. This form often reflects modern utopian experiments, emphasizing communal living and shared ideals.

Intentional Communities and Communal Living

Intentional communities, such as communes, represent Socially Constructed Eutopias where like-minded individuals work toward harmony and sustainability. The Israeli Kibbutzim, for example, formed in the early 20th century, aimed to embody socialist ideals through communal work and shared property (Avineri, 1968).

Digital Utopias

In the digital age, virtual platforms like *Second Life* offer users opportunities to construct utopian communities in online spaces. This digital paradise allows users to create idealized versions of themselves and interact in environments that transcend physical boundaries, reflecting humanity's enduring quest for paradise in both physical and virtual realms (Boellstorff, 2008).

Conclusion

Eutopia reflects humanity's diverse aspirations for an ideal existence, one that varies significantly across religious, philosophical, and cultural landscapes. Through religious promises of paradise, philosophical blueprints for ideal societies, and community-driven projects, these visions of Eutopia provide frameworks that guide human thought and behavior. While some are achievable through personal effort, others promise rewards beyond this life, and still others require the commitment of entire societies.

The concept of Eutopia ultimately illustrates humanity's drive toward a harmonious existence, even as it reminds us of the complexities and dangers inherent in our ideal visions.

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Abstract

The notion of heaven and hell has long been a subject of theological and philosophical discourse across cultures. In particular, the concept of *Samsara*, the eternal cycle of birth, death, and rebirth, presents a unique lens through which the notion of human suffering and the pursuit of enlightenment can be understood. This paper explores the hypothesis that human beings, caught in cycles of ignorance and error, often fail to learn from their mistakes, leading to recurring patterns of suffering. Drawing from Buddhist teachings and other philosophical traditions, the paper argues that the human condition, as exemplified by the tragic history of the Jewish people and their pursuit of a "Promised Land," serves as an illustration of the cycle of Samsara. The ultimate realization of the truth, however, requires breaking free from these cycles of ignorance and delusion.

Keywords: Eutopia, Jannah, Behesht, Paradise, Promised land, Israel-Palestine

Introduction

The human experience is often marked by cycles of suffering, ignorance, and error, which Buddhists refer to as *Samsara*—the wheel of birth, death, and rebirth (Davoudpour, A.R., 2024). Central to Buddhist teachings is the idea that ignorance (*avidya*) leads to suffering, and that breaking free from these cycles is essential for achieving liberation (*nirvana*). The concept of *Samsara* is not just a metaphysical or religious idea but can also be applied to historical and social contexts. This paper posits that the human propensity to repeat mistakes, as seen in historical tragedies such as the events surrounding the Jewish people and the Nazi regime followed by the cycle of crimes in the occupied land of Palestine and reflects the deeper patterns of ignorance and delusion inherent in the human condition. We already studied the concept of the Eutopia and Promised land in different categories of philosophy and religion (Davoudpour, A.R., 2024) in more details. The myth of the "Promised Land" and the realization of heaven on earth, especially in the context of the Israeli state and the criminal encounters in several folds both from Nazis and the Zionist governments, serves as an allegory for the endless cycles of *Samsara*, where the pursuit of a utopian ideal often leads to further suffering and violence.

The Cycle of Ignorance and Error in Human History

The hypothesis presented in this study is that humans, particularly those in positions of power or living in states of material affluence, are often blind to the consequences of their actions. They fail to learn from past mistakes and continue repeating them, either due to ignorance or willful disregard for the truth. The paper draws upon the Buddhist concept of *Samsara* to explain this phenomenon: humans, in their ignorance, fail to recognize the deeper truths of existence, and thus remain trapped in cycles of suffering.

One of the most poignant historical examples of this ignorance is the experience of the Jewish people. The story of the "Promised Land" and the eventual establishment of the Israeli state is fraught with tragic irony. The Jews, who endured centuries of suffering, displacement, and genocide, ultimately sought to create their own utopian society, only to find themselves embroiled in cycles of violence, territorial conflict, and the oppression of others. The paradox is that in their pursuit of a "Promised Land"—a vision of

heaven on earth—they inadvertently perpetuate suffering and injustice, repeating the same mistakes they once endured.

In this sense, the experience of the Jewish people exemplifies the Buddhist view of Samsara: the cycle of suffering is not simply about physical birth and death but is also about the repetition of harmful patterns, whether individual or collective. *Samsara* is, in essence, the inability to break free from ignorance and the cyclical nature of human behavior.

The Forbidden Fruit: A Buddhist Allegory of Enlightenment

The concept of the "forbidden fruit" is a metaphor that appears in various religious and philosophical traditions. In the Biblical narrative, Adam and Eve's consumption of the forbidden fruit in the Garden of Eden represents humanity's fall from grace, a transition from innocence to knowledge. Similarly, in Buddhist thought, the path to enlightenment involves overcoming the desires and delusions that keep one trapped in the cycle of Samsara.

In this paper, the "forbidden fruit" symbolizes the rejection of the status quo and the willingness to confront uncomfortable truths. The idea that "heaven" or utopia is an illusion, and that true enlightenment requires going beyond conventional social norms and political ideologies, resonates with Buddhist teachings on non-attachment and the impermanence of worldly phenomena (*anicca*). The pursuit of a perfect society—whether through religious or political means—often leads to further suffering, as it is rooted in the illusion of permanence and the inability to confront deeper truths about human nature.

Buddhist teachings emphasize that the pursuit of enlightenment is not a journey that leads to external rewards, but an inward journey of understanding. *Samsara* is driven by attachment to the self and a refusal to let go of illusions, whether they are related to wealth, power, or ideological purity. Thus, the "forbidden fruit" represents the breaking of attachments to false ideals and the willingness to embrace the difficult process of self-realization and truth.

Heaven and Hell in the Context of Social and Political Structures

The concept of heaven and hell is not only a theological one but also deeply embedded in social and political structures. In the case of the Israeli-Palestinian conflict, the notion of the "Promised Land" reflects a societal belief in a utopian vision that, when actualized, results in exclusion, violence, and oppression of the Other. The

establishment of Israel as a state, while a response to centuries of suffering, also perpetuates cycles of violence and suffering for others, illustrating the Buddhist idea that suffering is inherent in attachment to worldly goals.

The Israeli example, while specific, offers insights into the broader human condition. Whether one is striving for political power, territorial control, or religious purity, the Buddhist perspective reminds us that attachment to any worldly ideal without awareness of its impermanence and potential for harm will inevitably lead to suffering. *Samsara* manifests not only in personal attachments but in the collective behavior of societies that refuse to confront the deeper truths of their actions.

The Illusion of the "Promised Land"

The historical narrative surrounding the Jewish people is emblematic of the human tendency to seek a "Promised Land," a utopian destination that promises peace, prosperity, and justice. However, as history has demonstrated, such promises often lead to new cycles of suffering. This is where the Buddhist concept of *Samsara* provides a valuable framework: the cycle of desire for the "Promised Land" is just another form of attachment, one that prevents individuals and societies from seeing the true nature of their suffering.

The illusion of the "Promised Land" is akin to the illusion of *Nirvana* for many who misunderstand its true nature. In the Buddhist tradition, *Nirvana* is not a place or a state of pleasure but a state of liberation from suffering, achieved through the cessation of attachment. Similarly, the so-called "Promised Land" is not a place that can be reached through external conquest or domination, but rather a state of mind that requires the cessation of attachment to political ideologies, territorial claims, and historical grievances.

Conclusion: Breaking the Cycle of Samsara

The exploration of the cycle of *Samsara* and the illusion of the "Promised Land" offers profound insights into the human condition. As illustrated by the tragic history of the Jewish people and their quest for a utopian society, the cycle of ignorance, attachment, and suffering is not easily broken. The Buddhist path to liberation, however, offers a solution: by recognizing the impermanence of all things and understanding the nature of desire and suffering, one can transcend the cycle of *Samsara* and achieve true peace.

In Buddhist thought, true enlightenment comes not from the external attainment of power, wealth, or territorial control, but from an internal transformation of understanding and wisdom. This requires breaking free from the illusions that bind us to a false notion of heaven on earth and recognizing that true freedom lies in the cessation of attachment to worldly desires.

Ultimately, the journey toward enlightenment involves transcending the cycles of Samsara—whether personal, social, or political—and embracing a deeper understanding of the truth. In doing so, one can break free from the perpetual cycle of suffering and move toward true liberation. Such a deep virtual and ethical pursuit can not be easily broken with the advances in technology or science as it has been clarified in the stance of Gaza which until now has massacred and disabled hundreds of thousands of sentient beings.

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Abstract

The interplay between visions of utopia and the presence of justice and underworlds within human thought reveals critical insights into the cyclical nature of justice, suffering, and human consciousness. Drawing upon religious, philosophical, and social narratives, this paper examines the concept of utopia as both an aspirational goal and a hidden source of oppression, particularly when framed within the metaphysical context of underworlds and cyclical suffering. Using the Buddhist concept of *Samsara* (the cycle of birth, death, and rebirth) as a philosophical framework, this research explores how ideological constructs—whether religious, political, or cultural—manifest as "underworlds," shaping the realities of justice and injustice in the world. The paper argues that the pursuit of a utopian vision, when driven by ignorance or unattainable ideals or philosophical means i.e. Marxism, often perpetuates cycles of suffering and injustice, thus entrenching a human "underworld" that exists even in societies that perceive themselves as "heavenly."

Keywords: Eutopia, Jannah, Behesht, Paradise, Promised land, Justice, Underworld, Samsara

Introduction

The idea of an underworld—whether as a physical, psychological, or societal concept—has long been a central theme in human mythology, philosophy, and theology. It typically represents a state of suffering, punishment, or moral decay, often juxtaposed against idealized visions of utopia. Yet, what if these two constructs—utopia and the underworld—are not opposites, but intertwined realities within human existence? The paper investigates this hypothesis, examining how utopian ideologies, when pursued without an understanding of deeper truths, may serve as a mechanism for perpetuating cycles of suffering, creating "underworlds" within societies that seem to be striving for justice or perfection.

In this study, I apply the Buddhist concept of *Samsara*, the cycle of suffering and rebirth, as a model for understanding how human ideals of justice, utopia, and progress often result in recurring patterns of injustice and suffering. Drawing from various religious and philosophical traditions, I explore how societies—despite their visions of heaven or utopia—remain caught in cycles of violence, oppression, and suffering, which can be likened to living in an underworld. These cycles, once set into motion, can be self-perpetuating, as seen in the history of human civilization and particularly in the context of political, religious, and ideological struggles.

The Utopian Vision and the Hidden Underworld

The concept of utopia, as an idealized state of human perfection, is often envisioned as a paradisiacal existence free from suffering, injustice, and inequality. The ancient Greeks spoke of *Eutopia* (the good place), while more modern thinkers like Thomas More, in his *Utopia* (1516), presented a vision of a just, harmonious society. However, historical and contemporary events show that utopian ideals, when imposed without critical self-awareness or regard for the complexities of human nature, often give rise to their opposite—an underworld of suffering, oppression, and violence.

For instance, the establishment of a "perfect" state often involves the subjugation of "the other"—those who do not fit into the vision of that ideal society. This pattern is visible in numerous historical

events, such as colonialism, totalitarian regimes, and religious conflicts, where the pursuit of a utopian order led to the creation of societal "underworlds." These underworlds are not merely symbolic; they are tangible realities for the marginalized, oppressed, and excluded members of society.

In Buddhist thought, the illusion of a perfect world is central to the cycle of *Samsara*. The pursuit of attachment to idealized forms of existence, such as a perfect state or "heaven," leads to suffering because it is based on ignorance (*avidya*) of the true nature of reality. This ignorance blinds individuals and societies to the inherent impermanence of all things, leading them to chase fleeting ideals that inevitably result in conflict, disillusionment, and suffering. As the Buddha taught, *dukkha* (suffering) is not merely physical pain but includes the mental suffering caused by attachment to false ideals.

In the context of political ideologies, the pursuit of utopia is often driven by an underlying desire for justice. Yet, as history has shown, such ideals are rarely achieved without significant human cost. Whether through warfare, systemic oppression, or the marginalization of dissenting voices, the quest for a utopian society often creates "underworlds" for those who stand in opposition or fail to conform to the new order.

Justice, Suffering, and the Cycle of Samsara

At the heart of this research is the idea that justice, as pursued by societies, is often entangled with suffering and cyclical repetition. In Buddhism, *Samsara* represents the perpetual cycle of birth, death, and rebirth, driven by ignorance and desire. This cycle is not merely a metaphysical concept but also a reflection of the social and political cycles that govern human life. Justice, in many cases, becomes another ideal to be pursued without regard for the underlying causes of suffering.

The Buddha's teachings on *dukkha* reveal that suffering is not simply an external reality but an intrinsic aspect of the human condition, arising from our attachment to the self and our misconceptions about the world. In this sense, the cycle of *Samsara* is not just an individual process but a collective one. The suffering experienced by one person—whether through war, discrimination, or exploitation—creates ripples that affect society as a whole, perpetuating the cycle of injustice.

In examining historical examples, we see how political ideologies and utopian visions often contribute to cycles of injustice. The Holocaust, for example, can be seen as a tragic manifestation of the pursuit of a "pure" utopian vision by the Nazis. The vision of a racial utopia, in which only the "Aryan" race would thrive, led to the creation of an underworld for millions of Jews and other marginalized groups. The resulting genocide exemplifies how the pursuit of ideological justice can create massive suffering and entrenched cycles of violence and hatred.

The Marxist Theory of Justice: A Materialist Perspective

Marxist theory begins with the premise that human beings are shaped by their material conditions. Justice, then, is not a universal principle or an abstract moral law but a product of historical and social circumstances (Marx, 1867). Marx's theory of justice is rooted in the concept of historical materialism, which asserts that economic structures and relations of production shape social institutions, laws, and even moral values (Marx & Engels, 1846). In this context, justice cannot be understood outside the system of material production and the class relations that emerge from it. As Engels (1846) highlights in his work *The Condition of the Working Class in England*, the material conditions of society directly influence the ideologies that justify the existing order, including its conception of justice.

Similarly, the establishment of colonial empires was driven by the belief in the superiority of certain cultures and the desire to "civilize" the rest of the world. Yet, this utopian vision for a better world often resulted in the violent subjugation and exploitation of entire populations, creating underworlds of suffering in colonized regions that persisted long after the colonial powers had left (Fanon, 1963). This dynamic is illustrative of Marx's broader critique of how dominant classes or nations impose their vision of justice while perpetuating exploitation and inequality in the name of progress or civilization.

1. The Role of Class Struggle

In Marxism, the concept of justice is inherently connected to the dynamics of class struggle. Marx sees society as divided into two primary classes: the bourgeoisie (the capitalist class that owns the means of production) and the proletariat (the working class that must sell its labor to survive). Marx (1848) argues that in a capitalist society, justice is always skewed in favor of the bourgeoisie, as the

legal and political systems are designed to perpetuate their economic dominance. The existing state and its institutions function to maintain the status quo, serving the interests of the capitalist class and suppressing any challenges to their rule.

Marx contends that true justice can only be achieved through the overthrow of capitalist systems and the establishment of socialism—a system where the means of production are collectively owned, and the resources of society are distributed according to need rather than profit (Marx & Engels, 1848). The achievement of social justice, from a Marxist perspective, involves dismantling the economic and social structures that perpetuate inequality and exploitation. This transformative process requires a revolutionary change, as Marx (1867) suggests, in which the working class must seize control of the state apparatus and redistribute power, wealth, and resources more equitably.

2. Justice as the Abolition of Exploitation

For Marx, exploitation is the fundamental injustice of capitalist society. In his analysis of labor and value, Marx (1867) argues that the value of goods and services produced by workers is greater than the wages they are paid. The difference between the value of what is produced and what is paid to the worker is called surplus value, and it is extracted by capitalists as profit. This surplus value is the source of capitalist wealth, and it arises from the exploitation of labor. According to Marx (1867), this extraction is a form of systemic injustice, as workers are not compensated for the full value of their labor.

Justice, therefore, in Marxist theory, means the abolition of exploitation. In a just society, workers would control the means of production and the distribution of wealth, ensuring that the value created by labor is returned to the workers who produce it. Justice is realized when workers no longer live under the oppressive conditions of wage labor and are free to determine their own conditions of life, work, and social existence (Piketty, 2014). As Marx (1867) famously writes, in a just society, workers would "reap the fruits of their labor," which would no longer be appropriated by capitalist owners.

3. The Abolition of Private Property

The Marxist quest for justice also involves the abolition of private property in the means of production. Marx (1867) does not mean the abolition of personal property—such as personal belongings—but

the collective ownership of the tools, resources, and institutions that produce wealth. Private property, as Marx sees it, is the foundation of capitalist exploitation, as it allows the bourgeoisie to extract surplus value from workers (Marx & Engels, 1848).

The abolition of private property would create a society in which resources are shared and wealth is distributed based on need rather than ownership (Marx, 1867). This transformation is essential for achieving justice because it would eliminate the class divisions that underpin capitalist society. Marx's vision of justice, therefore, is one of collective ownership and communal decision-making, where the means of production are used to meet human needs and not to generate profits for a small elite. Marx's critique of private property goes beyond its economic role, framing it as a source of social inequality and alienation (Marx & Engels, 1848).

In Marx's vision, justice is not merely about fair distribution, but also about the elimination of the social relations of exploitation that underlie capitalist production. The transition to socialism, he argues, would restore human dignity by abolishing the alienation workers experience under capitalism, thus providing a more just, equitable, and humane system.

The Role of Ideological Constructs in Perpetuating Suffering

The pursuit of utopia, whether driven by political, religious, or ideological motivations, often results in the creation of an underworld of suffering for those who do not fit the prescribed norms. In many cases, these ideological constructs are defended through laws, cultural narratives, and the creation of an "other" that can be blamed for societal ills.

In Buddhism, the concept of *Samsara* underscores the importance of recognizing the impermanence of all things. The attachment to any fixed ideal—whether of justice, peace, or a perfect society—inevitably leads to suffering. This is because such ideals are bound to the limited perceptions of human beings, who are often blinded by their desires, fears, and illusions.

In the case of the Jewish people and the establishment of Israel, for instance, the aspiration for a homeland after centuries of persecution has led to the creation of an idealized state. Yet, as history has shown, the pursuit of this utopian vision has involved violence, displacement, and the marginalization of the Palestinian people. The

creation of a "Promised Land" has, in this case, created an underworld for others—illustrating how the pursuit of one group's ideal can lead to the suffering of another.

Conclusion: Breaking the Cycle of Suffering

In light of the analysis, it becomes clear that the pursuit of utopia—whether in the form of political, religious, or social ideals—can lead to the perpetuation of suffering and injustice. This cycle of suffering, which mirrors the Buddhist concept of *Samsara*, is driven by attachment to illusory goals and the failure to confront the deeper realities of human existence. Breaking free from this cycle requires not just the realization of the impermanence of idealized visions but also the cultivation of wisdom, compassion, and awareness of the interconnectedness of all beings.

Ultimately, justice cannot be achieved through the pursuit of idealized worlds that disregard the complexities of human nature. Human quest to overcome suffering or to pursuit justice, is often deemed unsuccessful due to the convergence of wisdom, science and intellect (Davoudpour, A.R., 2024). True justice, from a Buddhist perspective, is achieved through the cessation of attachment, the recognition of suffering, and the cultivation of compassion for all beings with the means that equalize all. There has been attempts to refer Buddhism as a solely materialistic practice with the means of meditation and happiness, however the ultimate happiness can not be achieved without a form of transcendental guidance or indifference to the suffering of other sentient being. Only by breaking free from the cycles of ignorance and achieving certain levels of wisdom can humanity hope to transcend its underworlds of suffering and find true peace. That is where an interplay between metaphysics and human life i.e. religion comes to play. Although religion can be considered a primary sign of such significant source of understanding.

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